

THETIDA

THE EUROPEAN PROJECT FOR THE PRESERVATION OF UNDERWATER AND COASTAL CULTURAL HERITAGE

Athens, 08/04/2024

The Ephorate of Antiquities of Cyclades, as part of its research activities, announces its participation as a partner in the project THETIDA entitled "Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution".

Climate change, as revealed by gradual changes in temperature, precipitation, atmospheric moisture, and wind intensity, as well as sea level rise and changes in the occurrence of extreme events, is already affecting cultural and natural heritage sites, rendering their protection an international challenge. Correspondingly, there is a rapidly increasing body of research, reporting and actions aimed at ensuring the sustainability and preservation of cultural heritage at a global level.

The THETIDA project explores innovative and sustainable ways to safeguard Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage, particularly monuments, historical buildings, archaeological sites and coastal cultural landscapes from climate change effects, natural hazards and environmental pollution. Deployed sensors such as smart buoys, autonomous underwater vehicles, surface vessel sensors, wearable devices and micro-meteorological stations will be installed in pilot sites and complemented with remote sensing data and participatory processes. The data collected will support the development of a decision-making system that will provide effective emergency response and mitigation strategies for underwater and coastal sites of cultural interest. The project aims to raise awareness among stakeholders and local communities about coastal heritage protection processes through a mobile application to actively engage community groups and promote participatory actions. Livings Labs will be organized in demonstration areas to inclusively build roadmaps for active monitoring, protection and sustainable development of cultural heritage.

The Ephorate of Antiquities of Cyclades, responding to the need for coordinated international initiatives, participates in the THETIDA project by identifying the Castle of Mykonos Town as a relevant pilot site. The location of the monument and its exposure to geoclimatic risks, as well as to anthropogenic and natural factors, requires the immediate implementation of recording,

forecasting and protection methods that will create a protective shield for current and future challenges.

The program involves 17 partners from 8 different countries under the supervision and coordination of the Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS) of the National Technical University of Athens (NTUA).

Invitation

Within the framework of the program, we invite you to participate as collaborators in its implementation by attending workshops that will be organized by us in two stages, with the first stage scheduled for October 2024. The aim is to inform you about the significance and actions of the program, with the anticipation of your valuable contribution to the dissemination of information.

Sincerely,